

Article

Towards Zero Defect and Zero Waste Manufacturing by Implementing Non-Destructive Inspection Technologies

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Abstract: This study aims to provide an overview of Zero Defect, Zero Waste, and non-destructive inspection technologies (NDITs), which play a crucial role in the early detection of defects and material consumption in industrial processes. Integrating Zero Defect and Zero Waste strategies with non-destructive inspection technologies supports Industry 4.0 by using advanced sensors, robotics, and AI to create smart manufacturing systems that optimise resources and improve quality. The analysis covers the main functionalities, applications and technical specifications of several NDITs to automate the inspection of industrial processes. It also discusses both the benefits and limitations of these techniques through benchmarking. Deploying inspection as a service solution based on NDITs with data-driven decision-making Artificial Intelligence for in-process or in-line inspection policies increases production control by reducing material waste and energy use, and by optimising the final factory cost. After a comprehensive assessment, this paper aims to examine and review recent developments in the Zero Defects and Zero Waste field due to emerging non-destructive inspection systems, and their combination with other technologies, such as augmented reality. Advances in sensors, robotics, and decision-making processes through Artificial Intelligence can increase Human–Robot Collaboration in the inspection process by enhancing quality assurance during production.

Academic Editor: Yashar Javadi

Received: 13 December 2024

Revised: 14 January 2025

Accepted: 16 January 2025

Published: 21 January 2025

Citation: Lario, J.; Mateos, J.; Psarommatis, F.; Ortiz, Á. Towards Zero Defect and Zero Waste Manufacturing by Implementing Non-Destructive Inspection Technologies. *J. Manuf. Mater. Process.* **2025**, *9*, 29. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmmp9020029>

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Keywords: non-destructive technologies; sustainability; Zero Waste; Zero Defects; quality assurance

1. Introduction

In recent years, an increasing tendency in sustainable manufacturing techniques that helps industries move towards automatic non-destructive inspection (NDI) systems for quality assurance, which are reliable, easy to deploy, and readily available for in-line production environments, has become considerably important in the research community [1–3]. Industrial companies are moving from traditional quality methodologies and approaches like Six Sigma, Lean Manufacturing, and Total Quality Management, towards techniques whose goal is to achieve Zero Defects (ZD) in manufacturing industrial processes and Zero Waste (ZW) generated in quality acceptance procedures [4]. The Zero Defects and Zero Waste (ZDZW) methodology can be understood as the ultimate goal of the ZD Manufacturing (ZDM) approach, which initially emerged in the 1960s and has become considerably important in Japan in the last few years [5,6]. In other words, the ZDZW method is the implementation of ZDM with leading Key Performance Indicators (KPI) for Zero Waste [3,4,7].

ZDM aims to reduce defects and minimise the impact of both quality control and quality inspections by using data-based technologies, Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) algorithms [1,6,8]. Economical efforts made to help industries move towards non-destructive testing and ZW are a pressing, but mandatory challenge when discussing solutions to minimise the impact on the environment, and always in circular economy initiatives [9]. The integration of NDI technologies (NDITs) may optimise production, and reduce energy and material use, by decreasing the amount of resources needed during destructive testing for quality assurance purposes while keeping companies on the technological edge [10,11].

By implementing these technologies along with AI algorithms and Deep-Learning (DL) techniques, industrial production can be enhanced, while quality control can be extended to full production batches and not only to limited representative data. The need for new techniques that allow for passive testing that is non-disruptive, non-invasive and non-destructive, and is applied to industrial processes, has been a challenge in recent years [12]. Industry 4.0 focuses on integrating cyber-physical systems to optimise manufacturing using real-time data. Zero Defect Manufacturing approaches, enabled by NDITs and AI, support this vision by reducing waste, cutting energy use, and enhancing sustainability, driving automated and efficient production systems. That is where the main core on which ZDZW methodologies concept lies. The aim of this paper is to provide insights into new methodologies and industrial sectors where they can be applied.

Thanks to the constant monitoring of critical parameters (power input, layer deposition, argon pressure, etc.), process optimisation, and defect reduction strategies in the industry, their aim is to reduce the number of defective parts and generated waste to zero [2,13]. By also monitoring critical parameters during the process, it will be possible to correlate defects during the industrial process with external and internal factors of the process, which will allow for strategies to be carried out for the accurate detection, repair, prevention, and prediction of defects [2].

It is increasingly evident that the lack of raw materials in some critical sectors has pushed many industries to seek new methods that allow them to obtain competitive advantages, while aligning themselves at the same time with the objectives set out in European programmes, such as “Next Generation” and “SDGs: Sustainable Development Goals” [14]. It is necessary to continue implementing and deploying new inspection technologies in Europe to remain competitive in different industrial sectors, and to reduce the use of raw materials in industrial processes. Implementing non-destructive inspection technologies in manufacturing environments fosters the production process’s open eco-innovation, reducing waste and material consumption, and contributing to environmental sustainability [15]. The scope of the current paper is to perform a systematic analysis in the ZDZW domain and to provide comprehensive research for the NDITs and methodologies that will allow ZDZW to be implemented in European Union (EU) industries.

This paper is structured in seven sections. Section 2 evaluates the impact of ZDZW strategies on manufacturing sustainability and summarises the cost-benefit factors of NDITs. Section 3 presents a comparative analysis of different non-destructive inspection technologies that can be deployed to enhance manufacturing efficiency. Section 4 presents challenges and limitations for integrating NDIT, and the definition of engineering required to implement new inspection methodologies. Section 5, an industrial use case to highlight the importance of the adoption of NDIT, is presented. Section 6 analyses the impact of NDITs on social sustainability by considering human factors and discusses the importance of financial analysis in deploying these NDITs. The last section presents the conclusions by emphasising the importance of integrating NDITs into the in-process, on-machine and in-line inspections of defects in industrial processes.

2. Recent Advances in Non-Destructive Inspection Approaches

The manufacturing industry plays a crucial role in adding value to the European economy. It provides European society with critical inputs but is vulnerable to raw materials and energy price volatility because it depends on foreign countries. The deployment of new technologies that improve resilience must be examined for sustainable economic development. Additionally, ensuring a stable long-term supply of raw materials is a significant challenge, as the deployment of NDI for automatic inspection methodologies may help reduce their dependence. The competitiveness of the EU's industry directly and indirectly affects many other parts of the economy and the social welfare of EU regions. The implementation of hardware-/software-based solutions on small- to medium-sized manufacturers will offer possibilities to significantly reduce the cost expenditure of traditional quality assurance processes and to minimise raw material and/or energy use. ZDZW solutions will be able to detect defects during manufacturing (welding, painting, lithography, hardening, etc.) by NDI methodologies on a real-time basis.

The manufacturing of engineering parts for the aerospace, automotive, energy or biomedical sectors employs production methods with time- and energy-consuming procedures and multiple-step routes. China's rapidly growing production, the supply shortage due to the COVID-19 pandemic and Russia's invasion of Ukraine have made the price of raw materials (steel, polymers, plastic, etc.) and products go up because the EU depends on energy sources and raw materials. These facts have a negative impact on the EU industry sector's competitiveness. Increasing interest is being shown by the EU to implement ZDZW hardware/software technologies to improve manufacturing efficiency and boost economic competitiveness and profitability. Pressure to compete with EU foreign countries with lower salaries creates the need to optimise the technologies required to reduce costs (less material waste and energy used) and lead times. The aim of new hardware/software applications is to focus on applying an NDI and AI algorithms for in-process or in-line inspections on a real-time basis.

Several factors contribute to the inefficiency and lack of sustainability in industrial processes, such as excess material consumption or elevated defective rate [16]. These include low process repeatability, which increases material and energy uses, lead times and working inventories. All these costs reduce the economic profitability of industrial processes [17]. Another aspect is the high inspection cost and characterisation of parts by human intervention or destructive testing, which prolong manufacturing lead times, as well as intermediary inventories that present the related cost associated with managing them [7]. NDI solutions might represent a change in the quality assurance approach, which may have a direct impact on firms' business economic sustainability. Implementing an NDI system should ideally reduce waste and defects, which are key business objectives for any industrial company. Integrating NDI solutions is a promising path to achieving European manufacturing excellence [18].

Employing NDI systems can improve the parts working ratio because of shorter inspection times, less scrap production, or even fewer breakdowns. The evaluation of non-value-added activities (setups, breakdowns, scrap, reprocessing, inspection, etc.) should be analysed with performance measurements to confer management visibility. All these activities add cost to a manufactured part by reducing profitability but do not add value from customers' point of view. Companies should invest in activities, equipment, and projects that seek to lower the ratio between the value-added and total lead time. Industrial plants can reduce the non-value-added time, and lower the operational cost related to inventory, scrap, and uncertainty when implementing in-process or in-line inspections based on NDITs. The economic viability of a new NDI project should estimate and justify profits and operating costs compared to those associated with the presently employed

system in the production environment. The Table 1 summarises some factors related to NDITs' cost–benefit.

Table 1. NDIT cost–benefit factors.

NDIT Cost–Benefit Factors	
Reduction in annual operational costs	Product quality
NDI system depreciation	Reduction in scraps and defectives
Direct labour costs	Product quality
Indirect labour costs	Working capital
Saving in the direct/indirect materials	Saving in product recall
Saving energy consumption	Saving in non-conformities management
Increased productivity and capacity utilisation	Reduction in accidents to minimise many direct and indirect costs associated with injuries

This strategy aims to send feedback to the manufacturing operation to provide a process that falls within production control limits. For these purposes, NDI systems need to maintain production traceability, collect process and control data, and record inspection measurements to send feedback to the computerisation control system. For these purposes, the success of the NDI system relies on a strict data acquisition, management, and decision-making information system.

Psarommantis et al. (2020) presented a review highlighting the key factors and advantages of adopting new quality improvement strategies to address manufacturing defects, focusing on specific metrics and examples from various industrial scenarios [4]. Implementing NDI solutions may improve station idle time availability by improving the following indicators: rejected parts (production lost due to inferior quality) and setup times (production lost due to setup times). The capability of defect detection, identification, and quantification introduced by NDI systems provides advantages: increasing machine utilisation and improving parts' output rates per machine, thus lowering the number of pieces of equipment required to manufacture a part. From a literature review, the main direct, indirect, and intangible benefits that the NDI solution can add to the manufacturing ecosystem were extracted and are represented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. NDIT benefits in the manufacturing ecosystem.

The quality control performed on the final product is a detection strategy that allows for resources to be invested in parts' downstream operations, but it is not always usable. When product quality assurance is performed at the end of the transforming operation (machining, surface treatment, welding, painting, etc.) or before a packaging operation where a large amount of resources is employed, it results in considerable material and energy use that increases the final factory cost. If parts do not fulfil customers' requirements, sorting all batches and, in some cases, reworking or scrapping any non-conforming product may be necessary.

3. Comparative Analysis

In the past few decades, customers have required customised products of higher quality in shorter lead times to meet their requirements. Industries and/or companies should further invest in manufacturing research and development to create resilience and agile manufacturing processes to respond to new challenges. With the development of new sensors and the use of AI algorithms, in-process or in-line inspection systems open up a new way to improve manufacturing excellence with ZDZW strategies.

ZDZW strategies based on NDI systems can be considered an approach to improve manufacturing efficiency by real-time process control [14]. NDITs integrated with AI algorithms present some advantages: less human dependence, more reliable measurements, and a high automation level. These technologies are based on the information acquired by different types of sensors (optical, infrared, acoustic, etc.), and are processed with AI algorithms to extract relevant information and make good decisions.

This section summarises a qualitative and quantitative evaluation of the next-generation solutions for industrial manufacturing processes that comply with the ZDZW programme. These strategies include the use of inspection automation with a non-destructive sensor and ML algorithms to detect and classify defects, which will help to forecast deviations from optimal operating conditions [19–21] and, thus, prevent both equipment failure and anomalies during the production process.

3.1. Acoustic Emission

The AEs method is based on sampling acoustic waves by excitation from an external magnetic field or when the part is mechanically stressed [22]. After material excitation, certain strain energy or magnetic residual energy is released as a wave through the medium, which results in AE waves [23]. The AEs method is an NDIT that involves the detection, quantification, and analysis of the acoustic waves emitted in the medium [24,25]. Considerable attention has been paid to this methodology in recent years because it is useful in real-time monitoring applications and to further assess structural material integrity [26]. The sound signature is the result of changes that occur in the emitted sound waves that move through the part, which is the result of the interaction with the material microstructure, surface internal defects, and residual stress. The key parameters include, among others, rise time, cycle count, energy amplitude, and event duration, which provide an internal structural evaluation of specimens after manufacturing processing. Further analysis of the data collected by AE sensor filtering is required to reduce ambient noise interference [27]. Given the versatility of this technique and its non-destructive character, it can be applied in a wide range of industries, processes, machines, and materials, such as metals or composites [22]. Table 2 compares the AE technology to traditional inspection technology, such as ultrasounds or liquid penetrant testing. The main advantages of AE technology applied to quality assurance are that it allows for the inspection of parts in real time, has a high automation level and can be used to detect cracks, porosity, changes in microstructure, or even fibre breakages.

Table 2. Acoustic Emission technology benchmarking.

Criterion	AEs Transient Measurement	Ultrasound Testing	Eddy Current	Liquid Penetrant
Inspectable features	Cracks, manufacturing defects, fibre breakages [28–33]	Cracks, manufacturing defects [31–35]	Cracks, manufacturing defects, corrosion [36–39]	Surface pores or cracks
Detection depth	Up to 15 mm [32]	Very high (up to 200 mm) [34,40]	Surface (0.5–2.1 mm) [37,39]	Surface [41]
Minimum detectable damage	0.02–3.0 mm [29,31,32]	~0.02 mm [31,34]	–0.5 mm [37,39]	Depends on visual methodology
Materials suitable for inspection	All kinds	All kinds, except wood or paper	Only conductive materials	Non-porous metals
Real time	Yes	Yes	No	No
Inspection rate	Very low (0.1 mm/min) [42]	Very low (10 min) [31,41]	Low	Low (2–30 min per application) [39,41]
In-process or post-process	In-process	Post-process	Post-process	Post-process
Automation	High	High	Low	No
Accuracy	High	High	Low	Low
Cost-effectiveness	Low	High	Medium	High
Industrial scalability	High	Medium	Medium	Low

AE's non-destructive, non-contact nature allows real-time and automated inspections to detect cracks, porosity, microstructural changes, and fibre breakages. Compared to traditional methods like ultrasound or liquid penetrants, AE significantly enhances quality assurance processes thanks to automatization capabilities to deploy in-process inspections across various industries and materials.

3.2. Electromagnetic Acoustic Transducer

An electromagnetic acoustic transducer (EMAT) is an active non-destructive technique that relies on the interaction of two magnetic fields to generate ultrasonic waves in a given material [43], which can then be detected by a receptor placed at a certain distance. This NDT has the advantage of performing quality inspection with coupling-free sensors [44–47]. The present inspection methodology is ultrasonic technology in which excitation is generated directly in the material adjacent to the transducer. This effective technique has been proven for thick inspections, such as steel or aluminium materials, and when non-contact is required for inspections [35,48]. The EMAT is an ideal non-destructive and non-contact technology that is required to perform the automatic inspection of metal structures, such as railheads and wind tower structures, due to its permissibility to variable surface conditions and temperatures (Table 3). Inspection equipment can be integrated into submerged arc welding (SAW) equipment to automatically inspect seam welds in real time, and it provides information on weld integrity while consequent passes are applied. The main advantage of this inspection method is that it enables material and energy reductions because defects are detected and quantified during weld deposition. This enables the earlier detection of welding defects (cracks, pores, inclusions, etc.) compared to the conventional inspection techniques (ultrasonic, phased array, penetrant liquids, radiography, etc.) employed after all seam welds are deposited.

Table 3. Electromagnetic Acoustic Transducer technology benchmarking.

Criterion	EMAT	X-Ray	Eddy current	Piezoelectric Ultrasonic
High-temperature inspection	Yes [44]	No	Yes	No
Surface requirements	No [35]	No	No	Yes [49]
Real-time inspection	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Automation	Very high	No	High	High
Inspection in motion	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Inspection speed	Very high (1–9 mm/s) [50]	Very low [33,51,52]	Very high	High
Human interpretation	No	Yes [33,51,52]	Yes	Yes
Accuracy	High	Medium	Low	Low
Cost-effectiveness	Low	Very High	Medium	Medium
Industrial scalability	High	Low	Medium	Medium

EMAT is a non-destructive, coupling-free, non-contact inspection technology ideal for automatic metal structure analysis. It outperforms conventional methods by enabling earlier defect detection, tolerating variable industrial conditions, and reducing costs associated with post-process techniques like X-ray or radiography.

3.3. Infrared Technology

Infrared thermography (IR) records the surface temperature response of an object due to thermal energy. The IR sensors receive the emitted infrared waves from the material's surface and convert them into electrical signals, and, subsequently, into IR images [48]. The variations in the heat distribution provoked by an irregularity or defects are translated into a variation in the electrical signal measured by the IR sensor. IR can be considered a non-contact NDIT since it can detect anomalies or defects, such as pores, fractures, and contamination [53].

Infrared thermography can be divided into two main categories: passive (without external excitation) or active (with external excitation, such as eddy currents, lamps, lasers, etc.) modes. Thermal imaging technology uses infrared radiation due to the thermal energy of objects to gather information through images, even in low visibility environments. In active IR, the data are collected by material excitation from an external source. The passive thermography category is when the sensor measures the infrared thermal radiation energy generated by an object without an external source. Active infrared thermography heats materials' surface by external sources such as infrared lamps, halogen lamps, or hot air guns to create thermal pulses around 2–10 ms. The specifications of the IR hardware influence the precision and accuracy of the inspection, depending on the type of sensor, resolution, pixel size, and field of view, affecting the precision and accuracy of the inspection [27]. The IR technologies allow for the inspection of higher areas compared to other technologies such as pyrometers [13]. Thermal inspection systems using thermal images captured by thermal cameras have become the most efficient systems which are used to detect defects and anomalies in industrial processes such as thermoforming, heat-sealing, chemicals, plastics, welding, additive manufacturing, etc. [31,41].

Table 4 shows the main advantages of IR technology to be employed as ZDZW inspection solutions for in-process or in-line quality inspection since they are non-contact, real-time, and non-destructive inspection. This type of inspection technology can be used for real-time quality inspection of metallic additive manufacturing parts, such as stain-

less steel or titanium parts. Compared with conventional methods (Terahertz imaging or X-ray computed tomography), the main advantages of this technology are that it can be considered non-destructive, with elevated inspection speed, and can be employed for real-time inspection. IR is a non-contact, non-destructive technology enabling real-time defect detection in industrial processes. It offers high inspection speed, cost-efficiency, and suitability for in-process applications, outperforming traditional methods like Terahertz imaging or X-ray in accessibility and industrial deployment.

Table 4. Infrared Thermographic Technology Benchmarking.

Criterion	Thermographic Imaging	Terahertz Imaging	X-Ray CT
Non-contact	Yes [54]	Yes [54,55]	Yes [56,57]
Real-time inspection	Yes	No	No [33,56]
Non-destructive	Yes [57–59]	Yes [55]	No [51]
Inspection speed	High	Very low	Very low [33,56]
High sensitivity	Very low (0.12–0.5 mm) [36]	Yes 1.0–5.86 ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$) [55]	Yes 1–10 ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$) [33,56,60]
Penetration depth	5–24 mm [31,57,61]	High (up to 20 mm) [41,55,62]	Very high (working well up to 3–4.7–10 mm) [33,56,60]
Accuracy	Low	Medium	Low
Cost-effectiveness	Low	Very High	Very High
Industrial scalability	High	Medium	Low

3.4. Artificial Intelligence-Based Visual Inspection

Traditional visual inspection methods rely on inspecting predefined sampling parts, where operators manually inspect and employ measurement instruments like callipers, gauges, or micrometres. If the inspection batch is rejected, it can result in a high amount of scrap product, loss of added value tasks, and reduction in machine productivity. In most cases, quality control is performed by destructive testing, which reduces productivity and increases costs. Manual inspection is composed of repetitive and tedious tasks, which increase the operator's mental fatigue, reducing the defect detection accuracy and reliability compared with automatic vision systems [63]. To improve the accuracy and level of detectability, automatic Artificial Intelligence-based visual inspection solutions must be integrated into the production lines or manufacturing equipment.

The current trend in parts visual inspection is to move from human-based visual inspection to automatic visual inspection performed through digital sensors that capture the image and processes with the assistance of Artificial Intelligence algorithms for dimensional control or defect detection. Depending on the type of sensor employed, the visual inspection technologies may not fall within the visual spectrum wavelength, which can be beneficial compared with conventional human-based inspection methodologies. The visual inspection performed by the human eye is subjected to measurement conditions, operator subjectivity or interpretation, and visual fatigue can detect defects in the range of 1 μm [27]. In the past two decades, advanced industrial sectors, such as electronics or aviation, have benefited from integrating Deep-Learning algorithms into automatic visual inspection equipment [64]. These AI algorithms can extract and predict features by statistical methods, reducing the burning in preprocessing and fine-tuning tasks [12,65–71]. Higher levels of precision and reliability of Deep-Learning algorithms can be achieved by employing annotated defect datasets, obtained from a specific industrial use case. The

image acquisition hardware is another factor that influences the accuracy and performance of automatic visual inspection systems. Key factors include sensor size, resolution, speed, image stabilisation, optical lenses, and proper lighting [72–74]. These elements enhance defect detection by improving contrast, reducing interference, and highlighting defects. Automatic artificial visual inspection enhances in-process quality assurance with superior accuracy and reliability compared to manual methods. It enables 100% inspection, eliminating operator fatigue from repetitive tasks, and significantly improves quality assurance in industrial production environments.

4. Non-Destructive Inspection Applications

European industry should integrate digital transformation into quality assurance policies to enhance competitiveness and sustainability. Quality assurance is crucial in manufacturing because it ensures that products meet customer and regulatory specifications; poor quality costs fall within the manufacturing range from 5% to 30% of total income, considering repair, rework, inspection, recalls, and complaints [75]. This section analyses two scenarios for the wind energy sector in which engineering requirements were assessed to select proper hardware, software, and AI to develop the automatic NDI solution for in-process or in-line control activities.

The market share of renewable energy sources (i.e., wind power) will increase in forthcoming years due to the new strategies and policies adopted by the European Commission based on Agenda 2030 [76]. Currently, these efforts are being made according to SDG 7: affordable and clean energy. The main EU strategy objective is to ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable, and modern energy for all. The EU Green Deal sets the goal of making Europe the world's first emission-neutral continent [77]. In fact, the amendment of the Federal Climate Protection Act (2021) has tightened climate protection requirements by forcing countries to accelerate energy transition. There are methodologies and strategies that model how the transition should look in terms of energy supply, generation and logistics [77].

The expansion of renewable energy sources in energy production, which constitute 37.5% of the EU's overall energy generation, encompasses a diverse array of technologies [78]. These include wind power, solar power in its various forms (thermal, photovoltaic, and concentrated), hydropower, tidal power, geothermal energy, ambient heat harnessed through heat pumps, biofuels, and renewable waste components. In recent years, a growing renewable energy trend has been evident with the contribution of wind power (37.3% in 2021), which is the fundamental pillar on which this growth is based [78]. This ambitious objective will benefit citizens and related industries from this green energy transition. It is on this energy transition framework that our research focuses, which aims to meet the demand for faster, more efficient and accurate quality inspection services in the wind energy industry to achieve ZDZW resources [12,69,79].

Defining the technical specifications for each industrial use case is a recommended step when implementing an automatic inspection system. The correct definition will help the equipment manufacturer and customer agree on the requirements, accuracy, reliability, and inspection solutions to be used for the selected feature. A requirement for an NDI system or related software encompasses specifications, needs or expectations, which vary according to the industrial application, and considers hardware, functional, interface, communication, safety, and traceability, among others [48].

The occurrence of welding defects (pores, slag, fusion penetration) incurs a high reprocessing cost. Welding defects, such as porosity, may appear in the seam weld during fabrication due to incorrect parameter configuration (feed rate, voltage, build energy, etc.), external contamination, and variable weld pool dynamics due to an incorrect alignment

between the parts to be welded. Conventional non-destructive welding inspection testing techniques have the drawbacks of manual operator operations with very time-consuming processes. These conventional NDTs require a quality inspection to be performed when the manufacturing process ends, with a direct impact on lead times as opposed to a quick reaction to enable the adjustment of process parameters when NDTs are deployed. Typically, if the seam weld does not fulfil technical requirements after inspection, the weld needs to be grounded down or cut out to allow the part to be reprocessed. The time required to repair a section with a reference length of 1 m and a depth of 20 mm is estimated to be between 6 and 12 h, costing up to EUR 400–900 per metre. Implementing an EMAT for in-process quality inspection will provide valuable process control feedback to adjust welding parameters to improve productivity, reduce defective parts, enhance efficiency, and cut the total cost per manufactured tower.

The NDT survey in Tables 4 and 5 outlines the essential inspection requirements for evaluating the development of an automatic inspection for quality assurance by offering a research overview, and identifying relevant development topics. Table 5 focuses on the requirements and specifications for monitoring and inspecting the SAW process. The survey in Table 5 focuses on evaluating the steel microstructure after the heat treatment of bolts, which is required to improve steel’s mechanical properties. The targeted audience of the complete aforementioned tables are the software, electrical, material, R&D, quality engineers, and subject matter experts involved in integrating NDI solutions into manufacturing for in-line or in-process inspection purposes.

Table 5. Functional specifications and requirement assessments for welding in-process inspection.

Welding In-Process Inspection, Control, Rework					
Characteristic:	Seam weld inspection		Seam weld dimensions	Width:	Depth:
Manufacturing Technology:	<input type="checkbox"/> DED	<input type="checkbox"/> WAAM		<input type="checkbox"/> 1–10 mm	<input type="checkbox"/> 1–10 mm
	<input type="checkbox"/> SAW	<input type="checkbox"/> GTAW		<input type="checkbox"/> 10–20 mm	<input type="checkbox"/> 10–20 mm
	<input type="checkbox"/> PAW	<input type="checkbox"/> Other		<input type="checkbox"/> >20 mm	<input type="checkbox"/> >20 mm
Material:	Thickness metal sheet (mm):				
NON-DESTRUCTIVE INSPECTION				<input type="checkbox"/> Required	<input type="checkbox"/> Not req.
Type of inspection	<input type="checkbox"/> In-process	<input type="checkbox"/> Post-proc.	Microstructure evaluation	<input type="checkbox"/> Required	<input type="checkbox"/> Not req.
Mechanical properties	<input type="checkbox"/> Required	<input type="checkbox"/> Not req.	Chemical composition	<input type="checkbox"/> Required	<input type="checkbox"/> Not req.
Defects	<input type="checkbox"/> Cracks	<input type="checkbox"/> Porosity	<input type="checkbox"/> Voids	<input type="checkbox"/> Deposit	<input type="checkbox"/> Others
	Smallest detected defect		<input type="checkbox"/> <100 µm	<input type="checkbox"/> 100–500 µm	<input type="checkbox"/> >500 µm
Preferred technologies	<input type="checkbox"/> Laser ultrasonic		<input type="checkbox"/> Laser-induced breakdown spectroscopy		
	<input type="checkbox"/> Eddy current thermography		<input type="checkbox"/> Step-pulsed thermography		
	<input type="checkbox"/> Pulsed Thermography		<input type="checkbox"/> Multiple sensor		
	<input type="checkbox"/> Acoustic emissions		<input type="checkbox"/> Confocal		
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other _____				
Presently used inspection procedure	<input type="checkbox"/> Magnetic particle testing		<input type="checkbox"/> Liquid penetrant testing		
	<input type="checkbox"/> Radiographic testing		<input type="checkbox"/> Ultrasonic testing		
	<input type="checkbox"/> Eddy-current testing		<input type="checkbox"/> Phased Array		
	<input type="checkbox"/> Time of flight diffraction		<input type="checkbox"/> Others		

To install an offshore and onshore wind farm, it is essential that the bolted joints between the monopiles of the footing and between the ferrules of each span properly function. For this purpose, the final microstructure of bolts is an essential factor. To this end,

large-sized metric bolts of various lengths (up to 600 mm) are manufactured in hardened and tempered steels, high-strength materials, special stainless steels, and nickel alloys to secure the structure. However, destructive testing still applies for the quality analysis of these bolts, which results in wasted resources and the impossibility of extending these tests to the entire production. Faced with growing demand that increasingly requires a higher degree of customisation and shorter delivery times (Table 6), the in-process or in-line inspection by AE technology can assess mechanical properties and microstructures by analysing AEs when bolts are subjected to stress.

Table 6. Functional specifications and requirement assessments for steel in-line quality assurance.

Durable Fastening Inspection, Control, Rework					
Characteristic:	Fasteners		Heat treatment technologies:	<input type="checkbox"/> Induction	<input type="checkbox"/> Furnace
Shape Manufacturing Technology:	<input type="checkbox"/> Cold forging	<input type="checkbox"/> Hot forging	Cooling media:	<input type="checkbox"/> Vacuum Fur.	<input type="checkbox"/> Other
	<input type="checkbox"/> Cold rolling	<input type="checkbox"/> Hot rolling		<input type="checkbox"/> Oil quenching	<input type="checkbox"/> Water
	<input type="checkbox"/> CNC mach.	<input type="checkbox"/> Other		<input type="checkbox"/> Air	<input type="checkbox"/> Other
Material:	<input type="checkbox"/> Martensitic steels	<input type="checkbox"/> Duplex steels	Surface treatments:	<input type="checkbox"/> Electropolishing	<input type="checkbox"/> Passivation
	<input type="checkbox"/> Austenitic steels	<input type="checkbox"/> Other		<input type="checkbox"/> Electrodeposition	<input type="checkbox"/> PVP
				<input type="checkbox"/> Pickling	<input type="checkbox"/> Other
Part dimensions					
Minimum Ø	<input type="checkbox"/> >10 mm	<input type="checkbox"/> >20 mm	Maximum Ø	<input type="checkbox"/> <60 mm	<input type="checkbox"/> <80 mm
Minimum Length	<input type="checkbox"/> >10 mm	<input type="checkbox"/> >20 mm	Maximum Length	<input type="checkbox"/> < 60 mm	<input type="checkbox"/> <100 mm
Dimensional tolerance:	<input type="checkbox"/> <10 µm	<input type="checkbox"/> 10–50 µm	<input type="checkbox"/> >50 µm	<input type="checkbox"/> Other	
NON-DESTRUCTIVE VISUAL INSPECTION				<input type="checkbox"/> Required	<input type="checkbox"/> Not req.
Type of inspection	<input type="checkbox"/> In-process	<input type="checkbox"/> Post-proc.	Geometric accuracy	<input type="checkbox"/> Required	<input type="checkbox"/> Not req.
Laser marking inspection	<input type="checkbox"/> Required	<input type="checkbox"/> Not req.	Laser engraving inspection	<input type="checkbox"/> Required	<input type="checkbox"/> Not req.
Defects	<input type="checkbox"/> Cracks	<input type="checkbox"/> Porosity	<input type="checkbox"/> Voids	<input type="checkbox"/> Deposit peels	<input type="checkbox"/> Others
	Smallest detected defect		<input type="checkbox"/> <100 µm	<input type="checkbox"/> 100–500 µm	<input type="checkbox"/> >500 µm
Preferred technologies	<input type="checkbox"/> Laser ultrasonic		<input type="checkbox"/> Laser-induced breakdown spectroscopy		
	<input type="checkbox"/> Acoustic emissions		<input type="checkbox"/> Pyrometer		
	<input type="checkbox"/> Eddy current thermography		<input type="checkbox"/> Multiple sensor		
	<input type="checkbox"/> Pulsed Thermography		<input type="checkbox"/> Other _____		
Presently used inspection procedure	<input type="checkbox"/> Optical metallography		<input type="checkbox"/> Scanning Electron Microscopy Metallography		
	<input type="checkbox"/> Tensile testing		<input type="checkbox"/> Hardness testing		
	<input type="checkbox"/> Other _____				

5. Discussion and Future Directions

Digital transformation in inspection methodologies will allow manufacturers to implement in-process, in-machine, and in-line quality assurance policies to improve production efficiency and sustainability [80,81]. Deploying these new technologies in production environments reduces the operation inspection workload, decreases the percentage of scrap or reprocessing, and automates inspection systems by enhancing overall final product quality. Innovation on quality policy, founded on NDI, attempts to implement inspection systems to improve production capabilities based on a sustainable development decision

support strategy [82]. Each NDI technology presents its specific strengths and weaknesses, making them suitable for particular applications and materials. For instance, acoustic emission applied on steel materials provides a broad detectability range, including subsurface defects and information on defect location and shape on ferromagnetic materials. On the other hand, automatic visual inspection technologies are highly promising for parts with complex geometries but may face limitations in detectability and sensitivity. These constraints highlight the need to integrate and combine complementary contactless NDI methods and sensor technologies to enhance real-time defect detection, monitor process characteristics, and measure process parameters effectively.

The conventional manual inspection of parts is performed by destructive or non-destructive testing based on sampling methods, which impose a heavy physical and psychological workload for operators by prolonging lead times for being carried out off-line or in inspection areas, which lowers the produced part's profitability [83]. Repetitive tasks performed during inspection activities to ensure a certain quality level deplete operators' cognitive engagement and cause musculoskeletal disorders [84]. The proposed automated NDI inspection system, based on AI algorithms for the decision-making process, may incorporate autonomous guided vehicles (AGVs), collaborative robotic systems, and augmented reality solutions to enhance worker well-being by performing physical inspections [85]. This automatic NDI solution must operate collaboratively with installed safety features by improving process automation. Collaboration involves goal-oriented joint activities and also sharing capabilities, skills, and resources [75]. Compared to traditional isolated automatic inspection systems, human-robot collaborative automatic NDI systems involve three main design factors: safety, optimised task allocation, and human-robot interaction/adaptive control. The AI algorithm supports the decision-making process for defect detection and classification, and augmented reality helps to locate the position of the detected defect, and report it to the operator to perform the repair operation more quickly and easily [86,87]. To address the challenges of deploying AI-driven inspection systems, SMEs face hurdles due to high computational requirements and the labour-intensive process of creating balanced datasets. Techniques like data augmentation, transfer learning, and synthetic training data can help mitigate these limitations, enhancing their feasibility for SMEs. Multiple sensors and advanced technologies enhance ergonomics, working conditions, and overall process performance [84].

Advanced sensors (EMAT, AEs, IR, optical, among others), AI algorithms, and communication protocols facilitate in-process, in-machine, or in-line inspections by robotic systems. Integrating machine vision and LIDAR into AGVs allows for seamless interaction between operators and robots by enhancing coordinated activities [84]. Safety functions reduce physical workloads and improve operator conditions. Robots handle repetitive inspections of parts, while operators repair defects using augmented reality-provided information [88–92]. Automated NDI inspection systems that utilise human-centric solutions enable safe, dynamic, real-time decision-making in collaborative environments between humans and robots. In this new automatic NDI scenario, inspection systems integrate an HRC approach, the Augmented Reality Platform (ARP), allowing the defects acquired by NDITs and identified by the AI algorithm to be visualised. Thanks to the shop floor location of the AGV or collaborative robot, it will allow for interaction with the operator to perform repair tasks. Thanks to ARP solutions, operators can position a defect in a part and repair it before the part or item moves to the following operation or process step. These newly proposed scenario-based human-centric objectives involve reducing physical discomfort, decreasing mental fatigue, and increasing cognitive engagement with perceived self-efficacy.

Adopting NDIT solutions requires that small and medium enterprises (SMEs) comprehensively assess the financial aspects of these technologies in the manufacturing environment [93,94]. For these purposes, an economic evaluation needs to be considered, where topics such as Payback Period (PbP) and Return On Investment (ROI) should be addressed [95]. Usually, this kind of automatic inspection technology presents the drawback of being capital-intensive [96]. To overcome this significant blocking barrier, financial viability should be performed to evaluate the ROI and PbP to make decisions on a strategic level [97,98]. The economic evaluation of automatic inspection equipment, based on ZDZW solutions, remains consistent with conventional manufacturing equipment. Managers' or engineers' main goal is to achieve an economical rate of ROI, which is dependent on the returns achieved by installing the NDIT. For that purpose, the net revenue obtained from the reduction in material waste, energy consumption, and reduction in labour should be calculated. Conversely, the cost of acquiring and operating the NDI equipment must be estimated. The net revenue is divided by the total investment required to integrate the automatic inspection equipment to obtain the ROI value. Lario et al. (2024) proposed a cost breakdown model to evaluate the investment viability, allowing for the quantification of the ROI and PbP financial performance based on the degree of improvement in the first-time production ratio [98]. Integrating automatic inspection equipment that uses non-destructive technologies may deploy real-time detection capabilities to reduce material and energy consumption, decreasing the environmental impact of the current manufacturing operations and improving the first-time-right rate. The ROI value of automatic NDI equipment should consider the equipment cost, variations in labour requirement, material/energy consumption, and cost related to reprocessing [98,99].

New automatic inspection solutions that integrate non-destructive technologies based on ZDM strategies aim to enhance manufacturing sustainability by implementing in-process or in-line quality assurance for early detection of defects that may reduce scrap rates and energy consumption. Integrating NDIT minimises material waste, energy consumption, and scrap rates by ensuring efficient, defect-free production. These advancements reduce the carbon footprint, promote sustainable manufacturing, and align with Zero Defect manufacturing strategies focused on prevention and efficiency [99]. The potential of integrating non-destructive inspection technologies (NDITs) with advanced Product Life-cycle Management (PLM) systems to provide real-time feedback and predictive analytics. This integration could enhance the decision-making processes across the lifecycle stages, aligning more closely with Zero Defect and Zero Waste (ZDZW) objectives [100,101]. The ZDZW methodologies should be part of the smart manufacturing ecosystem, enhancing sustainable production through innovative quality assurance policies, automated inspection systems, ensuring traceability, and optimising operational costs [1]. The adoption of NDIT significantly impacts lead times and production costs by enabling automatic in-process inspections that replace manual methods [2,97,101]. This reduces cycle times, increases first-time-right rates, and minimises defect probabilities, improving production efficiency and sustainability. These advancements optimise manufacturing processes, ensuring cost-effective and reliable industrial operations

The deployment of ZDZW solutions on smart manufacturing ecosystems must be associated with key sustainability performance indicators to assess the impact on material and energy consumption and CO₂ emissions in manufacturing environments. The indicators should provide quantitative metrics to estimate the impact of automatic NDIT in the production processes. To achieve this milestone, the sustainable KPI should be based on historical data from production records to create a baseline for further evaluation. Once the ZDZW solutions are implemented in production, the effectiveness of sustainability will be evaluated post-implementation. The definition and creation of Sustainable KPI

should follow the criteria defined in ISO 22400, DIN EN ISO 14040:2006, and DIN EN ISO 14044:2006 norms to prevent misleading information and calculate emissions on the life cycle assessment (LCA) [102–104]. The ZDZW methodology emphasises innovation in automatic non-destructive inspection technology to improve quality assurance policies and assess the environmental impact thanks to Sustainable KPU, enabling new strategies and methods to improve manufacturing processes.

6. Conclusions

This work presents a general overview of NDITs, which play a crucial role in the in-process, on-machine and in-line inspection of defects in industrial processes. The deployment of automatic NDITs aims to gain competitive advantages in sustainable production by preventing defects throughout the production process and helping decision-making using artificial algorithms.

The present analysis considers the working principles of four NDITs, and the main principles for the platform that enable data acquisition, storage, and analysis for quality assurance purposes. The impact of NDITs stems from an operational perspective that is herein studied, and the main benefits of applying the ZDZW approach in the economic sustainability of the manufacturing environment are highlighted: less human intervention and waste, improved manufacturing lead times, and smaller intermediary inventories. Integrating human–robot collaboration into NDI tasks will improve worker psychological safety and contribute to a more sustainable and collaborative future in manufacturing because operators will centre their efforts on more value-added activities like repairing or reworking.

This research has emphasised the significant role of non-destructive inspection technologies in driving Industry 4.0 by facilitating Zero Defect and Zero Waste strategies, fostering sustainable manufacturing, and improving quality control by integrating AI and cyber–physical systems.

Author Contributions: All authors have significantly contributed to the conceptualization, design, data acquisition, analysis, or interpretation presented in this article. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: The ZDZW project received funding from the EU’s Horizon Europe programme with grant agreement No. 101057404. Any expressed views and opinions are, however, of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the EU. Neither the EU nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. The research leading to these results received funding from the Regional Department of Innovation, Universities, Science and Digital Society of the Generalitat Valenciana “Programa Investigo” (ref. INVEST/2022/400) within the framework of the Plan de Recuperación, Transformación y Resiliencia funded by the EU–NextGenerationEU.

Data Availability Statement: The raw data supporting the conclusions of this article will be made available by the authors on request.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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